

Prediction of survival in breast cancer patients using Random Forest classifier and ReliefF feature selection method

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Abstract— Studies have evaluated the use of machine learning to support clinical evaluation in cancer patients. Random Forest has demonstrated to be a relevant technique in predicting survival based on staging, treatment, prognosis, and patient characteristics. This study evaluated the performance of Random Forest classifier to predict the breast cancer patients' survival at starting the treatment phase in two different classes: up to or over 5 years; and evaluated performance by selecting the most relevant characteristics of the dataset using ReliefF feature selection method. The data were collected from the breast cancer patients' medical records. Altogether, 60 patient records were selected and the 10-folds cross-validation technique was used in the execution of Random Forest. Random Forest presented a significant result to predict the patients' survival, once its analysis demonstrated an accuracy of 91.67%, precision of 91.8%, F-Measure of 91.7%, sensitivity of 91.18% and specificity of 92.31%. Using the ReliefF method the accuracy was 93.33%, precision 93.3%, F-Measure 93.3%, sensitivity 94.12% and specificity 92.31%. It was possible to observe that the classifier presented excellent results of classification prediction. Therefore, this model could be recommended as a useful tool to predict the survival rate of breast cancer patients and to support medical decisions.

Keywords- classification; prediction; breast cancer patients; Random Forest classifier; ReliefF method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a chronic and multifactorial disease, characterized by uncontrolled growth of cells that can invade other tissues leading to metastasis and can promote severe metabolic, immunologic and endocrine alterations in the body, also can induce cachexia-anorexia syndrome, which can lead the patient to death [1], [2]. The patients can be treated by different types of anticancer therapies, such as surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy and hormone therapy, depending on the cancer stage and the patients' clinical condition, as well as, in accordance with the therapies available by the medical health system [3], [4].

Cancer incidence and prevalence have been increasing in an alarming rate worldwide and is considered the second leading cause of death [5]. Breast cancer is one of the main cancer types in Women [5]. In Brazil, breast cancer is the most common cancer and is one of the main causes of death in women [6]. In accordance with data from the National Cancer Institute (INCA), it is estimated that Brazil will have 625,000 new cancer cases in 2020, of which 66,280 will be new breast cancer cases [6].

Recent studies have evaluated the use of machine learning techniques to support the clinical assessment performed by the physician [7]. These tools assist in the diagnosis and can assist

in defining the most appropriate technique to be applied in the treatment of the patient. Vibha et al. [8] compared the Random Forest classifier and the algorithms Back Propagation and the Association Rule Classifier to confirm the diagnosis of tumor in breast cancer patients by mammography. Ghongade and Wakde [9] proposed to diagnose breast cancer patients using the machine learning method based on the Random Forest classifier using Fast Correlation-based feature Selection (FCBF) technique. Wang, Cheng, and Chiu [10] trained an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to predict the patients' five-year survival rate. Montazeri et al. [11] evaluated seven models of machine learning methods for the prediction of breast cancer survival in Iranian adult people, and it was observed that the best model to predict survival was Random Forest.

In addition, Wang et al. [12] adopted a tree ensemble classification method that took imbalanced data into account to evaluate the 5-year survival rate of colorectal cancer patient. It was obtained the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of 70.69%, 84.52% and 66%, respectively. Shouket et al. [13] evaluated six classifiers for the prediction of breast cancer survival. Concerning the 5-year survival rate, JRip and Random Forest classifiers had better accuracy, 96.25% and 95.83%, respectively.

Moreover, Singh et al. [14] evaluated a system and investigated the use of the AdaBoost feature selection method for the execution of the Random Forest to detect normal and abnormal mammography images. Ahmad and Yusoff [15] evaluated the classification of breast cancer lesions using the Random Forest classification method into two categories: benign and malignant cancer. Ganggayah et al. [3] researched machine learning techniques to build models for identifying the most important prognostic factors influencing the survival rate of breast cancer patients in the Asian setting, at the end, the Random Forest algorithm produced better performance using all data. Sun et al. [16] proposed a framework to detect cervical cancer patients based on Pap smear images using Random Forest classifier and ReliefF feature selection method.

Thus, this study aims to evaluate the performance of the Random Forest classifier to predict the breast cancer patients' survival rate at the beginning of the treatment phase into two different classes: up to 60 months (five years) or above 60 months (five years). The data were collected from medical records carried out by oncologist doctors of Santo Antônio's Hospital in Sinop, Mato Grosso, Brazil. Furthermore, the objective was also to evaluate performance by selecting the most relevant characteristics of the dataset using the ReliefF feature selection method in the Random Forest classifier.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The architecture of the article is described in Figure 1. The first step was the collection of real data from the patients' medical records. During the data preparation phase, some instances were removed due to lack of pattern, noises, and when they did not address the purpose of this article. Then, the features were selected, and the classifier was executed.

Figure 1. Classification architecture of data collected from the patients' medical records with breast cancer.

A. Data Collection

The data were collected from handwritten medical records carried out by oncologist doctors of Santo Antônio's Hospital in Sinop, Mato Grosso, Brazil. In total, 197 patients with breast cancer between 2013 and 2018 were analyzed. The research targets were female or male patients who were preliminarily diagnosed with breast cancer and received their entire treatment in the study hospital. The study and data collection were approved by the Hospital Ethics Committee and by the Ethics Committee for Human Study at Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso (protocol n. 2.414.600). In Figure 2 are listed the extracted data.

B. Data Preparation

Considering that data collection ended in December 2019 and this paper aims to predict the breast cancer patients' survival at the beginning of the treatment phase into two different classes: up to 60 months (five years) or above 60 months (five years), the data between 2015 and 2018 of alive patients were removed due to the impossibility to verify if these patients will survival up to or above five years.

The data between 2013 and 2014 of alive patients where on the day of data collection the patient had survived less than 5 years were removed, due to the impossibility to determine whether the survival of these patients was up to or above 5 years. The data between 2013 and 2018 of all the dead patients were considered. Some instances were removed due to lack of pattern, and noises. Thus, 60 patients' data were considered for prediction analysis.

General Patient Information	Anthropometric measurements	Data on the Patient's Clinical Status	Complementary Data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medical record number Entry date Medical insurance Date of birth Age Sex Marital status City / State Place of birth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Body weight Height Body surface Body mass index 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diagnosis Estrogen receptor expression Progesterone receptor expression Human epidermal growth factor receptor type 2 expression Tumor staging Type of therapy used Medicines prescribed Number of chemotherapy cycles Hormone therapy Radiotherapy Surgery Metastasis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diabetes Cardiovascular diseases Other incident diseases (e.g. infections) Medicines used before diagnosis Medicines prescribed during cancer treatment Prognosis Date of death (in case of death) Final survival Smoking General observations

Figure 2. Data collected from the patients' medical records.

C. Feature Selection

The data were organized, and the feature selection was based on clinical availability and [10], [11] and [7] studies. In the present work, were selected twelve features to predict the five years survival rate of the patients: age, sex, body mass index, estrogen receptor expression (ER), progesterone receptor expression (PR), human epidermal growth factor receptor type 2 expression (HER-2), tumor staging, hormone therapy,

radiotherapy, surgery, metastasis and diabetes. The class target was final survival which if higher than or equal to five years, set as 0, otherwise, set as 1. In Table I, the attributes of the dataset were described in detail.

To compare the performance of the Random Forest classifier, the features were also ranked based on the ReliefF algorithm, as seen in Table II. The features with positive weights - sex, body mass index, ER, PR, tumor staging, hormone therapy, radiotherapy, surgery, metastasis and diabetes - were selected and submitted to the classifier. ReliefF algorithm is used to identify which attributes are most relevant to the set of instances and available data. A weight is linked to each attribute, where the most relevant attribute has the highest weight. It is not limited to two classes problems, it is a robust algorithm that can handle noisy and incomplete data [17]. It was executed by the Weka program.

Sun et al. [16] evaluated the ReliefF algorithm to select the features of the dataset of cervical cancer patients and obtained significant results. Sangaiah and Kumar [18] proposed to combine the ReliefF and entropy-based genetic algorithm to select the features. From a total of 24,482, it was reduced to 75 features for classifying normal breast cancer patients, obtaining results with better accuracy.

D. Random Forest Classification

The Weka program version 3.8.4 (Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis) was used in the simulations proposed in this article, which has several implementations contemplated that facilitates data analysis and simulations.

The use of machine learning techniques is an important methodology for tumor detection and assessment of the survival rate of breast cancer patients [19]. The Random Forest classifier proved to be one of the most efficient techniques in this process as can be seen in [11] and [9]. This classifier is defined in [20] and [21]. In this study, it was used the technique 10-folds cross-validation. In this technique, the data set is divided into 10-folds and 10 training iterations are performed, in each iteration 9-folds are used for training and one fold for validation, the calculated performance is the average performance of the 10 iterations, as shown in Figure 3 [16].

Figure 3. Interactions that occur in the technique 10-folds cross-validation.

E. Analysis Classifier Performance

A normal method for evaluating the classifier result is to compare the classifier results with the current condition of the patients. This paper used the indicators accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F-Measure to evaluate the results classifier using the variables true positive (TP), false positive (FP), true negative (TN) and false negative (FN).

TABLE I. BREAST CANCER DATASET DESCRIPTION OF ATTRIBUTES.

Feature number	Feature description	Value	Amount	Proportion (%)
1	Age	<=30	0	0.00%
		31-40	6	10.00%
		41-50	16	26.67%
		51-60	21	35.00%
		>60	17	28.33%
2	Sex	Female	59	98.33%
		Male	1	1.67%
3	Body mass index	Normal weight	17	35.42%
		Overweight	14	29.17%
		Obesity	17	35.42%
4	Estrogen receptor expression	Positive	48	84.21%
		Negative	9	15.79%
5	Progesterone receptor expression	Positive	45	78.95%
		Negative	12	21.05%
6	Human epidermal growth factor receptor type 2 expression	Positive	11	20.37%
		Negative	42	77.78%
		Inconclusive	1	1.85%
7	Tumor staging	1	16	27.12%
		2	16	27.12%
		3	17	28.81%
		4	10	16.95%
8	Hormone therapy	Yes	42	71.19%
		No	17	28.81%
9	Radiotherapy	Yes	37	61.67%
		No	23	38.33%
10	Surgery	Yes	51	85.00%
		No	9	15.00%
11	Metastasis in another organ	Yes	22	37.93%
		No	36	62.07%
12	Diabetes	Yes	5	9.09%
		No	50	90.91%
13	Class target (final survival)	0	34	56.67%
		1	26	43.33%

TABLE II. LIST OF ATTRIBUTES RANKED USING THE RELIEFF METHOD.

Ranking	Feature	Weight
1	Metastasis	0.66222
2	Tumor staging	0.2375
3	PR	0.11056
4	Hormone therapy	0.07167
5	Diabetes	0.05167
6	Surgery	0.02167
7	Body mass index	0.01958
8	Radiotherapy	0.01833
9	ER	0.01722
10	Sex	0.00667
11	HER2	-0.02208
12	Age	-0.04833

PR: progesterone receptor; ER: estrogen receptor; HER2: human epidermal growth factor receptor type 2.

- True positive: breast cancer patients' who lived above five years and were correctly classified as patients who lived above five years;
- False positive: breast cancer patients' who lived up to five years and were incorrectly classified as patients who lived above five years;
- True negative: breast cancer patients' who lived up to five years and were correctly classified as patients who lived up to five years;
- False negative: breast cancer patients' who lived above five years and were incorrectly classified as patients who lived up to five years.

Based on these variables, the accuracy is defined by the proportion of instances correctly classified concerning the total number of instances. It can be obtained from Equation 1. Precision is the proportion of instances correctly classified concerning instances classified as positive, as described in Equation 2. Finally, F-Measure is the combined metric of precision and recall. This analysis demonstrates how precise and robust is the classifier, being described by Equation 3.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$F - Measure = \frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Precision + Recall} \quad (3)$$

Sensitivity or true positive rate (TPR) evaluates the positive instances correctly classified concerning the total number of

positive instances, that is, the proportion of patients who lived above five years and were correctly classified. This demonstrates the capacity of the algorithm to classify correctly the positive cases. It can be obtained from Equation 4.

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

Specificity evaluates negative instances correctly classified concerning the total number of negative instances, that is, the proportion of people who lived up to five years and were correctly classified. This demonstrates the capacity of the algorithm to correctly classify the negative cases. It can be obtained from Equation 5. The false positive rate (TPR) is equal to 1-specificity.

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (5)$$

Confusion Matrix		
Classified Positive	Classified Negative	
True Positive	False Negative	Actual Positive
False Positive	True Negative	Actual Negative

Figure 4. General confusion matrix for two classes.

Confusion matrix shows how many instances have been assigned to each class. In this study, we considered survival over 5 years as positive and survival up to 5 years as negative. Thus, the line "Actual Positive" in Figure 4 represents the number of patients who survived over 5 years, according to the data collected from medical records. And the "Actual Negative" line shows the number of patients who survived up to 5 years. However, the "Classified Positive" and "Classified Negative" columns represent the classification performed by the classifier.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study included data from 60 patients who started treatment between 2013 and 2018. In the classification based on the patients' survival status, 26 patients died within 5 years, which represented 43.33% of the total patients' population, and 34 patients survived above 5 years, 56.67% of the patients' population. In the classification based on cancer stage, the number of patients diagnosed as in Stage I to Stage IV were 16, 16, 17, and 10, respectively, accounting for 27.12%, 27.12%, 28.81%, and 16.95% of the data collected, respectively.

The 5-year survival rate predicted using the Random Forest classifier was compared to the original data as shown in Confusion Matrix in Figure 5. The "Survival above 5 years" line describes the number of patients who survived over 5 years, according to the medical record, which resulted in 34 patients. And the line "Survival up to 5 years" shows survivors up to 5 years old, which totaled 26 patients. However, the "Survival above 5 years" column presents the number of records classified by the Random Forest classifier as survivors over 5 years, and the "Survival up to 5 years" column describes the number of subjects classified as survivors up to 5 years. In Figure 5B, the

characteristics used in Random Forest were based on the selection of characteristics performed by the ReliefF algorithm. And in Figure 5A, we submit all the characteristics in the execution of the classifier.

A			B		
Confusion Matrix		← classified as	Confusion Matrix		← classified as
Survival above 5 years	Survival up to 5 years		Survival above 5 years	Survival up to 5 years	
31	3	Survival above 5 years	32	2	Survival above 5 years
2	24	Survival up to 5 years	2	24	Survival up to 5 years

Figure 5. Survival prediction results. A) Results using the Random Forest classifier. B) Results used the Random Forest classifier based on the selection of characteristics performed by the algorithm ReliefF.

Figure 6 presents the comparison between Random Forest classifier performance with or without the use of the ReliefF algorithm. It is possible to observe that the Random Forest classifier presented a significant result to predict the survival of these 60 patients, once its analysis demonstrated an accuracy of 91.67%, precision of 93.94%, F-Measure of 92.54%, sensitivity of 91.18% and specificity of 92.31%. Evaluating twelve features to predict the five years survival rate of the Brazilian patients by the Random Forest, it is possible to observe that the analysis was effective presenting excellent accuracy and sensitivity results.

Figure 6. Comparison between Random Forest performance with or without the use of the ReliefF algorithm.

Similarly, Ganggayah et al. [3] also evaluated machine learning techniques to build models for identifying the important prognostic factors influencing the survival rate of breast cancer patients. They analyzed a large dataset with 8066 data with diagnosis information between 1993 and 2016 and selected 24 variables for the analysis, observing that the Random Forest algorithm produced better performance using all data: accuracy of 82.70%, sensitivity of 83%, specificity of 81% and precision of 93%. Also, the six most important variables identified were cancer stage classification, tumor size, number of total auxiliary lymph nodes removed, positive lymph nodes, primary treatment types, and methods of diagnosis.

In the present study, to compare the performance of the Random Forest classifier, the features were also ranked based on the ReliefF algorithm, and it was possible to observe that using the ReliefF significant results were obtained, once the data demonstrated an accuracy of 93.33%, a precision of 94.12%, an F-Measure of 94.12%, sensitivity of 94.12%, and specificity of 92.31%, as shown in Figure 6. The features used in this analysis were: sex, body mass index, ER, PR, tumor staging, hormone therapy, radiotherapy, surgery, metastasis and diabetes.

Tapak et al. [7] evaluating eight models of machine learning methods for the prediction of breast cancer survival and metastasis in Iranian women, analyzed 9 different risk factors to compare the models and presented that the Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) were

the best models to predict survival, with the sensitivity of 73% and accuracy of 93%. However, LDA was the best model to predict metastasis, with an accuracy of 86% and precision of 61%. None of the methods had a sensitivity greater than 50% to predict breast cancer metastasis.

Wang, Cheng, and Chiu [10] also trained an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to predict the patients' five-year survival rate. The authors selected five variables, including age, tumor size, condition of tumor metastasizing to lymph nodes, whether the tumors had metastasized to other organs and whether breast-conserving surgery was performed followed by radiotherapy. The ANN method had an accuracy of 85.1%, sensitivity of 94.83% and specificity of 52.86%. Sun et. al [16] evaluated the combination of the Random Forest classifier with the ReliefF method to generate a reliable classification framework for the cervical cell images and compared the results obtained with the performance of the Naive Bayes, C4.5 and Logistic Regression classifiers. The results based on Random Forest with the top 13 features selected by the ReliefF method achieved the best performance in all the experiments evaluated [16].

Moreover, Wang et al. [12] proposed a two-stage model for advanced-stage colorectal cancer survival prediction, where the first stage was to predict whether a patient can survive more than five years. In the first stage adopted a tree ensemble classification method that took imbalanced data into account. In total, 1568 records with survival over 60 months and 1503 records with survival less than 60 months, were retained for classification experiments. It was 10-fold cross-validation, and the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity were 70.69%, 84.52% and 66%, respectively.

In addition, Shouket et al. [13] evaluated six classifiers to predict breast cancer survival in Pakistani patients, based on a record of 200 breast cancer patients and a data set consisting of 10 features. Concerning the 5-year survival rate, JRip and Random Forest classifiers had better accuracy, 96.25% and 95.83%, respectively. Montazeri et al. [11] evaluated seven models of machine learning methods for the prediction of breast cancer survival in Iranian adult people, selecting 9 attributes that are associated with the survival of breast cancer patients. The dataset included 900 patient records in which 803 patients were alive and 97 patients were dead. They compared the models by 10-fold cross-validation strategy and was used Weka software, observing that the best models to predict survival was Tree Random Forest with accuracy, true positive rate and precision of 96% and false positive rate of 24.1%.

IV. CONCLUSION

The models presented significant results. At first, twelve characteristics were selected to be submitted to the Random Forest classifier, where it obtained accuracy of 91.67%, precision of 93.94%, F-Measure of 92.54%, sensitivity of 91.18% and specificity of 92.31%. Then, the features were ranked based on the ReliefF algorithm and submitted again in the Random Forest classifier, obtaining an accuracy of 93.33%, a precision of 94.12%, an F-Measure of 94.12%, sensitivity of 94.12% and specificity of 92.31%. In this sense, this model proved to be a useful tool to predict the survival rate of breast cancer patients and to support medical decisions. A limitation of

this work is the number of records available, as a suggestion it is possible to consider a longer period and perform the classification again to evaluate the accuracy of the results.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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